

1 **Micellar Liquid Chromatography Determination of Rivaroxaban in Plasma and Urine.**

2 **Validation and Theoretical Aspects**

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27 **Abstract**

28 A Micellar Chromatographic method to determine rivaroxaban in plasma and urine has been
29 developed. The samples were dissolved in the mobile phase (SDS 0.05 M – 1-propanol 12.5 %,
30 phosphate buffered at pH 7) and 20 µL directly injected, avoiding the extraction and purification
31 steps. Using a C18 column and running under isocratic mode at 1 mL/min, analyte was eluted
32 without interference from the matrix in less than 6.0 min. The detection absorbance wavelength was
33 set to 250 nm. The procedure was validated by Food and Drug Administration guidelines in terms
34 of: system suitability, calibration range (0.05 – 5 mg/L), linearity, sensitivity, robustness, carry-over
35 effect, specificity, accuracy (-11.1 to 4.2%), precision (<19.9%), stability and analysis of incurred
36 samples. The method was found reliable, practical, easy-to-conduct, rapid, relatively eco-friendly,
37 safe, inexpensive, widely available and with a high sample throughput. The method was applied to
38 the analysis of incurred samples, including incurred sample reanalysis, to verify that the
39 instrumentation works correctly. In addition, the constants of the different partition equilibria
40 occurring in the column were elucidated in order to have a better comprehension of the theoretical
41 aspects of the retention mechanism. A moderately strong association between rivaroxaban and the
42 stationary phase and the micelles was found, weakened by short chain alcohol.

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47 *Keywords:* Anticoagulant; Biological Fluid; Direct injection; Micellar Chromatography; Partition
48 equilibrium; Validation.

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53 **1. Introduction**

54 Rivaroxaban (RIV, Fig. 1) is an oxazolidinone belonging to the group of the direct or novel
55 oral anticoagulants (DOAC or NOAC, respectively) commonly used to prevent blood clots. Its
56 activity is attributed to a potent, irreversible and selective inhibition of free and clot bound Factor
57 Xa [1-10], thus blocking thrombin generation [11-15]. RIV was the first DOAC and was approved
58 by FDA in 2011. It is currently one of the most prescribed anticoagulants [11]. RIV is indicated to
59 treat and/or prevent thromboembolic disorders, like venous thromboembolism (VTE), deep vein
60 thrombosis (DVT), pulmonary embolism, *etc.* It is used for the prophylaxis of VTE after total
61 orthopedic hip or knee replacement therapy and stroke or systemic embolism in patients with atrial
62 fibrillation [1-15]. It is not recommended for prescription in patients under 18 years old, pregnancy
63 and those with severe renal or liver failure [2,10,11]. RIV may cause excessive bleeding at overdose
64 [11]. Its therapeutic and adverse effects are closely related to the plasmatic concentration
65 [2,4,10,12,15].

66 RIV displays a more favorable benefits-to-risk profile than conventional anticoagulants. It is
67 administered orally and rapidly absorbed by the gastrointestinal system. It has high efficacy and
68 tolerability, a rapid onset of action, predictable pharmacokinetics (Table SM1) and
69 pharmacodynamics, large therapeutic window (nearly 6 to 491 µg/L [2,12]), a low risk of
70 interaction with food, absence of accumulation in patients without co-morbidities, low likelihood of
71 adverse effects and rapid elimination. Clinical effects are dose-dependent and no patient-adapted
72 dosage is usually required. In fact, RIV can be prescribed at a fixed daily dose for the most patients
73 [1-12,16,17].

74 Therapeutic Drug Monitoring (TDM) of RIV in a given individual may be relevant in
75 certain circumstances in order to guide the decision making about the treatment ensuring the
76 optimum efficacy. Plasma levels might be influenced by several factors altering the drug
77 metabolism exposing the patients to a significant risk of under- or over anticoagulation. The direct
78 quantification of RIV in plasma is preferred for drug testing [1-5,7-9,13-17], although in urine is

79 also feasible [3,9,14,15] and has the advantage of being non-invasive. The level of RIV in plasma
80 reflects the presence of the drug at a specific point in time, since in urine infers the exposure for an
81 extended period [9]. Therefore, clinical laboratories require rapid and sensitive analytical assays
82 able to identify and quantify RIV in both biological fluids to implement an effective TDM
83 approach.

84 Micellar liquid chromatography (MLC) using a C18 column, and anionic sodium dodecyl
85 sulfate as surfactant, and short-chained monoalcohol as organic modifier has been proven a reliable
86 tool for the determination of drugs in plasma and urine [18], avoiding the major drawbacks of
87 hydro-organic HPLC: use of sophisticated/expensive detectors and devices, need of large,
88 cumbersome and variable-recovery extraction or purification steps, use of a large quantity of
89 hazardous chemicals, extensive manipulation, *etc.* Indeed, micellar solutions are able to solubilize
90 small drugs [18]. Besides, micelles and monomers strongly interact with proteins, lipids, glycosides
91 and other macromolecules, usually present in the biological fluids, provoking its denaturing,
92 solubilization, releasing bounded drugs and preventing further interaction with the analytes [19]. In
93 the column, these biopolymers remain solubilized in the micellar mobile phase without risk of
94 precipitation, and are barely retained, being harmless eluted at the front of the chromatogram.
95 Therefore, after a sample dilution, the biological fluids, can be directly injected in the
96 chromatographic system [18]. Hybrid micellar solutions contain innocuous and biodegradable salts,
97 and only up to 12.5% of organic solvent [20]. The retention mechanism in MLC depends on two
98 partition equilibria for moderately hydrophobic solutes (bulk hybrid micellar mobile phase –
99 micellar pseudo phase; bulk hybrid micellar mobile phase - monomer-modified stationary phase).
100 Besides, the chromatographic behavior of a solute can easily be predicted from the composition of
101 the mobile phase, using equations constructed from the three-phase model [21].

102 The aim of the work is develop a reliable, rapid, practical, easy-to-handle and inexpensive
103 procedure to determine RIV in plasma and urine by MLC. The method will be fully validated to
104 evaluate its analytical performance and used in incurred plasma samples and commercial

105 pharmaceutical formulations to ensure its suitability for routine analysis. Another goal was to
106 investigate the interaction of RIV with the different chemical environments occurring in the
107 column, for a better comprehension about the theoretical aspects of the retention mechanism and the
108 role of the main components of the mobile phase on the retention factor, by calculating the
109 physicochemical constants of the corresponding partition equilibria.

110

111 **2. Experimental**

112 *2.1 Standard and chemicals*

113 Powdered standard of Rivaroxaban (purity>99.4%) was purchased from InterQuim
114 (Barcelona, Spain). Sodium dodecyl sulfate (>99%), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, >99.6%) and
115 sodium dihydrogen phosphate dihydrate (>99%) were bought from Scharlab (Barcelona, Spain).
116 The solvent 1-propanol (HPLC grade) came from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Hydrochloric acid
117 37% was from J.T. Baker (Phillipsburg, NJ, USA). Sodium hydroxide (>98%) was purchased from
118 Riedel-deHaën (Hannover, Germany). Ultrapure water was *in-lab* produced using an ultrapure
119 water generator device Simplicity UV (Millipore S.A.S., Molsheim, France), from deionized water,
120 provided as tap water by the university. All aqueous solutions were prepared using this water.

121

122 *2.2 Preparation of solutions and mobile phases*

123 To prepare the micellar solutions, the adequate amount of SDS and $\text{NaH}_2\text{PO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$
124 (according to the desired concentration) was solved in ultrapure water and the pH was fixed to the
125 selected value by adding drops of HCl or NaOH solutions. Then, the appropriate volume of the
126 organic solvent (depending on the chosen proportion) was introduced, and the volumetric flask was
127 filled up with ultrapure water. Finally, this solution was ultrasonicated for 5 min to attain a
128 complete solubilization and filtered through a 0.45 μm -Nylon membrane filters (Micron
129 Separations, Westboro, MA, USA), with the aid of a vacuum pump, to remove solid particles.
130 These solutions were kept in amber bottles (to avoid bacterial growth) at room temperature.

131 A stock solution of rivaroxaban of 100 mg/L was prepared by weighing the proper weight
132 and dissolving it in DMSO. The working solutions were made by dilution of the stock solution in
133 mobile phase. These solutions were stored in a fridge at 4°C.

134

135 *2.3 Chromatographic conditions*

136 The chromatographic system was a HP1100 (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA)
137 equipped with an isocratic pump, a degasser, an autosampler and an UV-Visible absorbance diode
138 array detector (DAD), connected to a PC. The software Agilent Chemstation (Rev. B.04.03(16)
139 2010) was used to control the instrument, visualize and register the signal, and the measurement of
140 the chromatographic parameters (dead time, t_0 , retention time, t_R and peak area, PA). The
141 experimental dead time was 1.0 min. Retention factor (k), efficiency (number of theoretical plates,
142 N) and tailing factor (T) were calculated as in [22].

143 The stationary phase was in a C18 Kromasil C18 column (AkzoNobel, Amsterdam, The
144 Netherlands) with the following parameters: 150 x 4.6 mm; 5 μm particle size; 10 nm pore size.
145 Injection volume and absorbance wavelength were 20 μL and 250 nm, respectively. The mobile
146 phase was an aqueous solution of 0.05 M SDS - 12.5% 1-propanol buffered at pH 7 with a
147 phosphate salt. It runs under isocratic mode at 1 mL/min. All the analyzed solutions were filtered
148 through a 0.45- μm Nylon membrane filter (Micron Separations) with the aid of a 3 mL syringe, and
149 then introduced in the chromatographic vial. The special care of the chromatographic
150 instrumentation required when working with micellar mobile phases can be seen in [23]. Under
151 these conditions, the column has a lifespan of at least 1000 injections [23].

152

153 *2.4 Sample collection and processing*

154 The study was approved by two local Ethics Committees, Hospital and the University Ethic
155 Committee for Analysis of Research Projects. Written informed consent was obtained from all
156 participants and all research was performed in accordance with the 2013 Helsinki Declaration

157 principles. Plasma and urine samples from patients and healthy volunteers were provided by a local
158 Hospital, after consent of doctors and patients. The “healthy volunteers” do not take any medication
159 and their blood is free of drugs. They were six: three men and three women, and, for each gender,
160 one in his/her twenties, another in his/her thirties and the last one in his/her forties. For
161 confidentiality reasons, the samples from the patients were sent unlabeled. No personal and clinical
162 information about the patients or the healthy volunteers (except that indicated above) was provided
163 from the Hospital. The laboratory undertakes to do not transmit any information to other institutions
164 (except that here indicated).

165 The blood was collected using a BD SST tube (SBD Vacutainer Systems, Plymouth, UK),
166 and centrifuged at +4°C at 3000 rpm for 10 min (3000 x g), to get the non-cellular fraction, which
167 was immediately frozen and stored at -20°C. The reference validated and accredited standard
168 method used by the Hospital includes this kind of tubes, then no loss of RIV at this step is expected.
169 Urine samples were collected in glass tubes and kept at the same temperature. Afterwards, these
170 samples were sent to the laboratory, where they were kept under the same conditions. A matrix-
171 matched blank was made by mixing equivalent volumes of the plasma or urine, respectively, of the
172 six healthy volunteers.

173 Plasma and urine, either blank or patient samples, were treated in the same way. The
174 samples were thawed until the onset of melting, the same day of the analysis. Afterwards, an aliquot
175 was 1/5-dissolved in mobile phase, filtered and directly injected [21]. The fortification was
176 performed by adding the appropriate volume of a standard solution of Rivaroxaban, before the
177 dilution. All the validation studies “in matrix”, for these biological fluids, were performed using
178 spiked blank samples.

179

180 **3. Results and discussion**

181 *3.1 Optimization of the chromatographic conditions*

182 The main chromatographic conditions to optimize in MLC method [18,21] are: surfactant,
183 modifier concentrations and pH. Using C18 and SDS as column and surfactant, respectively, the
184 stationary phase is saturated with SDS monomers adsorbed on its surface, with the sulfate group
185 oriented to the mobile phase, at concentrations > 10 mM, slightly over the critical micellar
186 concentration (CMC) of 8 mM. Working above this concentration, SDS monomers in the mobile
187 phase are organized as micelles, which number per volume unit is proportional to the initial
188 concentration of SDS. The amount of free monomers remains nearly constant and equal to the
189 CMC. Therefore, we can work at relatively low concentration of surfactant (recommended working
190 concentrations 0.05 - 0.15 M) in which the mobile phase has a low viscosity and low background
191 signal.

192 According to the moderate hydrophobicity ($\log P_{o/w} = 1.7$) of RIV [11], a pure micellar
193 mobile phase would provide too long capacity factors. Therefore, 1-propanol was added to reduce
194 the retention time and, additionally, enhance the efficiency. The studied interval of concentrations
195 for 1-propanol was that recommended in MLC, 2.5 to 12.5% [18].

196 The effect of the pH was studied at 3, 5 and 7, all of them inside the working range of the
197 C18 column (2.5 - 7.5), by the analysis of a working solution of 0.5 mg/L of RIV. At pH 3, no peak
198 was observed, and at pH 7 the best peak appeared with a nearly Gaussian shape at reasonable
199 retention time. Therefore, these values were taken as optimal. According to the acid/basic activity
200 of RIV (pK_a 1.0 and 13.4), the molecule is neutral under the working conditions [11].

201 The qualitative influence of the SDS and 1-propanol on the elution parameters was
202 examined. A working solution of RIV (0.2 mg/L) was analyzed using nine mobile phases selected
203 following an experimental design based on a face-centered composite design plus the central point.
204 We take the combination of the minimum (-1) and maximum (+1) levels for both factors ($2^2 = 4$
205 assays), the combination of the average value (0) of one of them and the minimal and maximal of
206 the other one ($2 \times 2 = 4$ assays), and the combination of the average values (1 assay). The -1/0/+1
207 values were the minimal, average and maximal concentration of each component recommended in

208 MLC, respectively [24]. The composition of the assayed mobile phases and the results are shown in
209 Table 1. From these results, we deduce that RIV has a binding behavior face to the micelles in the
210 mobile phase, as the retention factor and the efficiency decrease at increasing values of SDS-
211 micelles. By the way, the elution strength of the mobile phase and the efficiency grow up at higher
212 values of 1-propanol, as usual in reverse phase MLC. The optimal mobile phase composition was
213 set to 0.05 M SDS – 12.5 % 1-propanol – pH 7. The analyte elutes at a short time, but far from the
214 expected front of the chromatogram for biological fluids [18], and the efficiency is maximal.
215 Therefore, the chromatographic analysis of a diluted sample can be carried out in only 6.0 min,
216 using a low amount of organic solvent and a simple isocratic program.

217 Detection conditions were optimized by Agilent ChemStation Rev. B.04.03(16) 2010
218 software. Absorbance spectrum of rivaroxaban (200 – 500 nm) was on-line measured at the
219 maximum height during the chromatographic run, in order to obtain its spectrophotometric
220 properties in the same micellar environment as used for the analysis. The maximum of absorbance
221 was found at 250 nm, and then this value was selected to maximize the signal-to-noise ratio. For
222 peak purity studies, the absorbance spectra were taken at different points of the peak (at half-height
223 and 0.1-height, both fronting and tailing), and they show the same shape as above.

224

225 *3.2 Determination of the partition physicochemical constants*

226 According to the three-phase model, in MLC using pure micellar solutions, the solutes are
227 partitioned between three phases: surfactant-modified stationary phase, bulk aqueous solvent, and
228 micellar pseudo-phase. The equilibria are described by two partition constants: K_{AS} (between the
229 bulk mobile phase and stationary phase; thus increasing the retention) and K_{AM} (between the mobile
230 phase and the micelles, thus decreasing the retention). Therefore, K_{AS} and K_{AM} quantify the degree
231 of interaction of the solute with the modified stationary phase and the micelles, respectively. In
232 hybrid micellar mobile phases, we assume that this model is also applicable, but the organic solvent
233 displaces the equilibria. This is only applicable at low concentration of organic solvents (<22 % for

234 1-propanol), as higher values causes the disaggregation of the micelles. We introduce two constants,
 235 K_{AD} and K_{MD} , which evaluates the shift in the equilibrium to the solvent and the micelle,
 236 respectively, with respect to the pure micellar solution (thus decreasing the retention in both cases).
 237 According to this three-phase theory, in MLC the retention factor of a moderately hydrophobic
 238 solute can be modeled from the concentration of surfactant and alcohol by the following
 239 mechanistic equation [18,20]:

$$k = \frac{\Phi K_{AS} \frac{1}{1 + K_{AD}\varphi}}{1 + K_{AM} \frac{1 + K_{MD}\varphi}{1 + K_{AD}\varphi} [SDS]} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

240
 241 where Φ is the phase ratio (volume of stationary phase divided by the volume of mobile phase in
 242 the column), φ is the proportion of 1-propanol in %, v/v and [SDS] in (M). If $\varphi = 0$, the constants
 243 K_{AD} and K_{MS} are removed from the equation, and if [SDS], the retention is ΦK_{AS} (as in
 244 hydroorganic HPLC). The equation may be reorganized to:

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{\Phi K_{AS}} + \frac{K_{AD}}{\Phi K_{AS}} \varphi + \frac{K_{AM}}{\Phi K_{AS}} [SDS] + \frac{K_{AM}K_{MD}}{\Phi K_{AS}} [SDS]\varphi \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

246
 247 Eq. 2 was fitted using the experimental values of k obtained from the experimental design (Table 1),
 248 by curve-fitting non-linear least-square regression (5 freedom degrees) [25], in order to calculate the
 249 physicochemical constants. An adequate goodness-of-fit was reached ($R^2 > 0.991$). The values of the
 250 constants were: $\Phi K_{AS} = 45.3$; $K_{AM} = 44.9$; $K_{AD} = 3,9$ and $K_{MD} = 0.15$.

251 A moderate/strong interaction was found between both the stationary phase and the micelles
 252 with RIV, probably by hydrophobic interactions. The presence of 1-propanol significantly modifies
 253 the two equilibria towards the bulk mobile phase, by the resulting increase of the hydrophobic
 254 interactions in the bulk mobile phase. However, the occurrence of 1-propanol barely affects the

255 interaction of the analyte with the micelles.

256

257 *3.3 Method validation*

258 The method was fully validated under guidelines of the FDA guidance for Industry,
259 Bioanalytical Method Validation 2018 (developed for analysis of biological fluids) [26] and several
260 guides about validation of chromatographic methods [18,27]. The general parameters were
261 determined in plasma samples: system suitability, linearity, calibration range, sensitivity, robustness
262 (as the results are similar for both biological fluids [28]), while specificity, carry-over effect,
263 accuracy and precision were separately determined for plasma and urine. Stability was determined
264 in stock solution, diluted plasma and urine, and plasma and urine.

265

266 *3.3.1 Specificity*

267 The ability of the procedure to distinguish the analyte from endogenous compounds of the
268 biological fluids was evaluated. The following analyses were performed: plasma (Fig. 2A and Fig.
269 2C, respectively) and urine (Fig. 2B and 2D) were analyzed before and after fortification at 1 mg/L.
270 Additionally, the absorbance spectrum was measured at five points as in 3.1.

271 In blank samples, a broad band (<3.5 min) was observed at the beginning of the
272 chromatogram, corresponding to proteins and other macromolecules, strongly associated to the
273 micelles, thus enough far from the analyte [18]. The baseline was quite stable, and no peaks were
274 visualized close or at the window time of the analyte. In the fortified samples, no peaks were
275 observed near or partially overlapping the analyte.

276 The following experiments were performed to assess the peak purity:

- 277 - For plasma and urine, the spiked samples were compared to those non-fortified. The
278 chromatograms show similar shape, except the peak corresponding to RIV.
- 279 - The chromatograms from processed samples were overlaid to that obtained in 3.1, and the peaks
280 assigned to the analyte were alike.

281 - The absorbance spectra were compared and were found rather similar, regardless of the time
282 taken, and were comparable to that obtained in 3.1.

283 These results point to the absence of compounds co-eluting with RIV, in the different
284 matrices. Therefore, the method provides reliable qualitative and quantitative signals about the
285 analyte.

286

287 3.3.2 System suitability testing (SST)

288 The main chromatographic parameters and their variability were determined, in order to
289 dispose of reference values to further check the normal running of the instrumentation and evaluate
290 the reproducibility of the chromatographic response. A blank plasma sample fortified at 2.5 mg/L of
291 drug was injected by n = 6. The evaluated parameters and acceptance criteria were: tailing factor,
292 1.41, <0.8-1.6; retention factor, 3.64, >2.0; number of theoretical plates, 2325 >2000; RSD of the
293 retention time 1.3%, <1.5% and RSD of the peak area 1.4%, <1.5%. According to the results, the
294 chromatographic response is enough consistent and useful for a reliable qualitative/quantitative
295 analysis.

296

297 3.3.3 Calibration range and linearity

298 Several blank plasma spiked samples containing increasing concentrations of RIV were
299 prepared in the range 0.025 – 5 mg/L, and analyzed by triplicate. The average peak area (PA) values
300 (response variable) and the corresponding concentration (independent variable) were processed by
301 least-square linear regression [29]. The slope was 119.8 ± 0.6 and the y-intercept was 0.7 ± 0.6 . The
302 reliability of the model was verified by the following tests:

303 - The residuals were homoscedastic, as the variances of the observed variable at the different
304 concentration levels (calculated from the PA replicates) were found equal ($p = 4.1\% < 5\%$).

305 - No trend was detected for the residuals, by visual examination of a plot residual *v.s.* concentration.

306 - No outliers were found in the regression model: the relative residuals were <1.66% (acceptance

307 criteria <3) and the Cook's squared Distances were <0.5 (acceptance criteria <1) for all points.
308 - The y-intercept confidence (0.7 ± 0.7) interval includes zero, then no systematic error was noticed.
309 - A significant correlation was found by a t-test on r ($p=0.000\%$, acceptance criteria $<5\%$) and
310 comparing the model and residual variance by a F test ($p=0.000\%$, acceptance criteria $<5\%$).
311 - The determination coefficient ($r^2 = 0.9997$) and the relative residual standard deviation ($<1.3\%$)
312 meet the acceptance criteria (> 0.990 and 5% , respectively) and then an adequate linearity was
313 found between the two variables in the studied interval. The lower limit of quantification (LLOQ)
314 was the lowest concentration fitting the acceptance criteria for accuracy and precision, 0.025 mg/L,
315 and the upper limit of detection (ULOQ) was 5 mg/L.

316

317 *3.3.3 Sensitivity*

318 The limit of detection is the smallest concentration of RIV injected that provides a peak
319 clearly differentiable from the baseline noise, whereas the limit of quantification was the minimal
320 concentration of analyte that can be reliably determined. These parameters were calculated as 3.3
321 and 10 the standard deviation of the y-intercept; 0.008 and 0.025 mg/L. The calibration range
322 covers the expected range of concentrations in patient's incurred sample (Table SM1), except the
323 lower range, between 8 and 25 $\mu\text{g/L}$ [3,8,13]. However, the no-detection of RIV points to the
324 absence of therapeutic concentrations of the drug (under $6-8$ g/L).

325

326 *3.3.4 Carry over effect*

327 The possible increase of the signal due to the presence of analyte remaining from previous
328 injections was investigated. For each biological fluid, two blank samples, fortified at the ULOQ (5
329 mg/L) and unfortified, were consecutively analyzed. No peak was observed at the window time of
330 RIV in the chromatogram obtained from the blank. Therefore, the occurrence of cross
331 contamination was considered negligible.

332

333 *3.3.5 Accuracy and precision*

334 These parameters were determined in matrix at four levels: LLOQ, 0.1; 0.25 and 2 mg/L.
335 Six samples were successively prepared and analyzed in the same run. The accuracy was the
336 closeness of agreement (in %) between the average value of the found concentrations and the true
337 value, while the within-run precision (repeatability) was the dispersion (RSD) of the obtained
338 concentrations. The effect of time in the variability was studied. The same experimental protocol
339 was conducted five different days (using renewed solutions) over a three-month period. The
340 between-run precision (intermediate precision) was the relative standard deviation of the five
341 average values of found concentration. The results are shown in Table 2.

342 All the values were under the acceptance criteria (for LLOQ <20% and for higher levels,
343 <15% [26]), the method provides adequate quantitative values for bioanalysis. These performances
344 were reached by the use of an easy-to-handle dilution as sample preparation, where the sample is
345 quantitatively introduced in the column with the absence of extraction / purification steps,
346 decreasing the subsequent sources of variance and the risk of analyte loss.

347

348 *3.3.6 Robustness*

349 The variation of the main chromatographic responses (retention factor, peak area and
350 efficiency) was examined at small, but deliberate, changes in the main operational parameters.
351 These were changed from their optimal value, and the tested oscillations were that we considered
352 that may occur during the laboratory work and chromatographic run, in a usual situation. The
353 studied factors and the studied interval were: A) detection wavelength ± 5 nm; B) SDS in mobile
354 phase ± 0.05 M; C) 1-propanol in mobile phase ± 0.2 %; D) pH in mobile phase ± 0.2 ; E) flow-rate
355 ± 0.05 mL/min and F) injection volume $\pm 2\mu\text{L}$.

356 A blank plasma sample spiked with 2.5 mg/L was analyzed by testing eight different set of
357 experimental conditions, which value was fixed by an experimental design following a Youden
358 approach [30]. Differences >8.0% were judged significant, meaning that they may be especially

359 controlled during the analysis. The retention factor was significantly affected by the concentration
360 of SDS in mobile phase and the flow-rate, the peak area by the concentration of SDS and the
361 injection volume, and the efficiency by the flow and the injection volume. Therefore, these factors
362 operational parameters must be especially controlled during analysis to achieve adequate analytical
363 results.

364

365 *3.3.7 Stability*

366 The degradation of RIV was studied in the below mentioned chemical environments and
367 external conditions. In each case, the tested conditions were those likely to be encountered during
368 the actual storage, handling and analysis, either in a Hospital or a clinical laboratory. The stability
369 was examined by the monitoring of the concentration of RIV/nominal value (0.2 mg/L in the
370 injected solution, in all cases) and the emergence of peaks from the decomposition products. The
371 degradation was considered significant if >5% for standard solutions and 15% for processed and
372 unprocessed biological fluids.

373 The experiments were conducted as follows. For all the cases, no new peaks were detected
374 and the concentration of RIV remains quite invariant, and then the drug was found stable during the
375 studied periods.

376 a) Stock solutions: A standard solution of 0.2 mg/L was prepared and stored in amber vials in a
377 fridge at +4°C. Each day, for two months, the solution was thawed, analyzed and re-introduced in
378 the fridge. Therefore, the analyte is stable during this period, and the working standard solutions can
379 be safely used without introducing a systematic error in the results.

380 b) Bench top Processed Sample Stability: Samples from both biological fluids were diluted and
381 placed in the autosampler. For one day, the samples were injected each hour (six replicate
382 injections). Standard Operating Procedure indicate that, each day, all the samples received by the
383 laboratory can be diluted and afterward injected in the chromatograph successively in the same
384 sequence run, up to 240 analyses. Could be used in QC (quality control) and system suitability

385 solutions to-be-analyze. This optimization of time management permits to increase the number of
386 samples that can be analyzed in a day and the productivity of the laboratory.

387 c) Long term storage of the biological fluids: a set of 15 spiked samples of plasma and urine were
388 stored at -20°C in the darkness. Each day, a sample was analyzed (six replicate injections).
389 Therefore, the biological fluids should be analyzed up to 15 days after sampling.

390 d) Long term freeze-and-thaw for the biological fluids: a fortified sample of plasma and another of
391 urine were kept at -20°C in the darkness. Each day (15 days), they were thawed, an aliquot was
392 analyzed (six replicate injections), and reintroduced in the freezer. Therefore, an individual sample
393 can be stored and analyzed several times at least during this time, albeit undergoing abrupt
394 temperature changes, without affecting the reliability of the results.

395

396 *3.4 Analysis of incurred samples*

397 The suitability of the assay was evaluated by the analysis of biological samples provided by
398 a local Hospital. QCs samples were incorporated, using spiked samples of plasma and urine. System
399 Suitability Test, blank samples, quality control (QCs) and Incurred Sample Reanalysis were also
400 performed. All the samples were analyzed in the same run. The results can be seen in Table 3.
401 Samples of plasma and urine with the same number correspond to the same patient. The
402 chromatogram obtained from the analysis of plasma and urine samples from patient 4 is shown in
403 Fig. 2E and 2F, respectively.

404 The results of the SST comply with acceptance criteria, indicating that the instrument
405 components are roadworthy and ready to perform the analyses. In all the incurred samples, RIV
406 peak was observed without overlapping from endogenous compounds. No unknown peaks or cross
407 contamination were detected in the blank QCs. The quantitative results of the other QCs (same
408 acceptance criteria as accuracy in 3.3.5) and the reanalyzed incurred samples (difference <20%)
409 were close to the nominal and the previous found concentration, respectively, thus pointing to the
410 absence of drift in the measurements. Despite the high number of analysis (44 injections), the entire

411 batch was examined in a short period, with a minimal participation of an operator, and using
412 available instrumentation, laboratory material and reagents. Besides, the volume of hazardous
413 chemicals manipulated and wasted, as well as the charge associated to waste treatment, is rather
414 limited. Therefore, the practical performances of the method allow its implementation in a clinical
415 laboratory.

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417 *3.5 Application to drug monitoring*

418 The procedure was applied to determine the pharmacokinetics of RIV in a healthy subject, in
419 order to prove its suitability to this sort of clinical studies. Following oral administration of a single
420 20-mg tablet to a healthy volunteer, the plasma was extracted each hour over 12 h and analyzed.
421 The chromatograms were similar to those obtained in 3.4. The peak corresponding to the analyte
422 was observed and none metabolite or interfering compounds were detected. Figure 3 depicts the
423 curve RIV concentration *v.s.* time after ingestion. Peak-plasma was reached at nearly 2 h, and the
424 C_{max} was 0.2 mg/L. The elimination half-life was 4.5 h.

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428 **4. Conclusions**

429 The use of micellar liquid chromatography with direct injection of the samples has been
430 demonstrated as a valuable alternative for the determination of RIV in plasma and urine. The main
431 advantage is, without doubt, the shortening and simplification of the sample preparation. In
432 addition, the analyte was eluted in less than 6.0 min and clearly identifiable and quantifiable. In
433 spite of the occurrence of macromolecules in the matrices, analyte was detected without
434 interferences and kept up stability in the column. These advantages were achieved because of the
435 remarkable properties of micellar solutions to bind and solubilize biopolymers and drugs. The
436 method was rapid, easy-to-handle, semi-automated, economic, ecofriendly, safe, with a high sample

437 throughput, and useful for a laboratory with a large workload, like a clinical one. The procedure
438 was rigorously and fully validated in terms of system suitability, specificity, linearity, calibration
439 range, sensitivity, carry-over effect, accuracy, precision, robustness, stability and analysis of
440 incurred samples (including blanks, QCs and ISR in the same batch); and the results fit the
441 acceptance criteria. The procedure was found suitable for determination of RIV in the two studied
442 matrices for clinical purposes. Finally, the retention equilibria in the column were investigated,
443 from the data obtained using an experimental design of only 9 assays, by chemometrics. The
444 binding between RIV and both micelle and stationary phase were moderately strong and essentially
445 by hydrophobic interaction. The binding was weakened by the occurrence of 1-propanol in the bulk
446 mobile phase.

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453 **6. Conflict of interest disclosure**

454 The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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456 **7. References**

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565 **FIGURES**

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570 **Figure 1.** Structure of rivaroxaban or (S)-5-chloro-N-{{2-oxo-3-[4-(3-oxomorpholin-4-yl) phenyl] oxazolidin-5-yl} methyl} thiophene-2-carboxamide.

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587 **Figure 2.** Chromatograms obtained by the analysis of: plasma A) blank, C) fortified at 1 mg/L with
 588 RIV and E) from patient 4; and urine B) blank, D) spiked at 1 mg/L of RIV and F) from patient 4.

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600 **Figure 3.** Plasmatic concentration-time profile of RIV after single ingestion of a 20-mg tablet by a
 601 healthy volunteer (the measured concentrations are shown with the same unity as the y-axis).

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613 **TABLES**

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615 **Table 1.** Chromatographic parameters of rivaroxaban depending on the composition of the mobile phase (Experimental
616 dead time was 1.0 min)

[SDS] (M)	1-propanol (%)	t _R (min)	Efficiency (number of theoretical plates)
0.05	2.5	10.03	1362
0.05	7.5	6.71	1418
0.05	12.5	4.64	2029
0.10	2.5	5.92	1104
0.10	7.5	4.34	1275
0.10	12.5	3.28	1912
0.15	2.5	5.08	913
0.15	7.5	3.53	1189
0.15	12.5	2.78	1763

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619 **Table 2.** Accuracy and precision studies (%)

Matrix	Level	Accuracy ^a	Within-run Precision ^a (repeatability)	Between-run (intermediate) Precision, %
Plasma	0.025 mg/L	-11.1	19.9	18.5
	0.1 mg/L	+5.6	7.4	6.9
	0.25 mg/L	+3.8	5.5	6.1
	2 mg/L	+0.0	1.2	1.4
Urine	0.025 mg/L	-9.5	17.4	16.2
	0.1 mg/L	+5.0	9.1	8.4
	0.25 mg/L	+4.2	7.0	5.8
	2 mg/L	+0.2	1.5	2.3

620 ^an=6; ^bn=5

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627 **Table 3.** Analysis of incurred samples (Px indicated the patient's number).

Sample	[Rivaroxaban]
Blank plasma sample (1 mg/L) x6	Fit the acceptance criteria (see section 3.3.2)
Plasma QC (0.075 mg/L)	0.069 mg/L
Plasma P1	0.125 mg/L
Plasma P2	Not detected
Plasma QC (0.2 mg/L)	0.190 mg/L
Plasma P3	0.420 mg/L
Plasma P4	0.090 mg/L
Blank plasma QC	Not detected
Plasma QC (0.5 mg/L)	0.470 mg/L
Plasma P5	0.321 mg/L
Plasma P6	0.259 mg/L
Plasma QC (0.075 mg/L)	0.070 mg/L
Plasma P7	0.128 mg/L
Plasma P8	0.032 mg/L
Plasma QC (0.2 mg/L)	0.185 mg/L
Plasma P9	0.059 mg/L
Plasma P10	0.226 mg/L
Plasma QC (0.5 mg/L)	0.523 mg/L
Plasma P3 reanalyzed	0.392 mg/L
Plasma 6 reanalyzed	0.228 mg/L
Urine QC (0.075 mg/L)	0.072 mg/L
Urine P1	0.821 mg/L
Urine P2	0.059 mg/L
Urine QC (1 mg/L)	1.123 mg/L
Urine P3	4.826 mg/L
Urine P4	0.685 mg/L
Blank urine	Not detected
Urine P5	3.325 mg/L
Urine P6	2.394 mg/L
Urine QC (2.5 mg/L)	2.387 mg/L

Urine P7	0.995 mg/L
Urine P8	0.325 mg/L
Urine QC (0.075 mg/L)	0.083 mg/L
Urine P9	0.587 mg/L
Urine P10	1.715 mg/L
Urine QC (1 mg/L)	0.926 mg/L
Urine 2 reanalyzed	0.318 mg/L
Urine 5 reanalyzed	3.654 mg/L
Urine QC (2.5 mg/L)	2.323 mg/L

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647 **SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL**

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649 **Table SM1.** Chemical and pharmacokinetic characteristics of Rivaroxaban [2,5,8,10-13]

Characteristic	Value	Reference
Solubility in water	Almost insoluble	[5,13]
Molecular weight	436 g/mol (small molecule)	[5,13]
Bioavailability	Doses up to 10 mg: 80-100%, regardless of the food intake. For 15 and 20 mg doses, it has a lower bioavailability in the fasted state, and then must be taken with food	[11]
Time to peak-plasma	2-4	[11]
Half-life	5-9 adults; 11-13 elderly	[11]
Protein binding	92-95%	[11]
C _{max} for doses 5 - 60 mg	40 to 400 µg/L	[12]
C _{through} for doses 5-60 mg	8 to 160 µg/L	[12]
Elimination	Urine (66%): 36 % as unchanged drug and 30% as metabolites Faeces (34%): 7 % unchanged and 21% as metabolites	[15]
Major or active circulating metabolite	None	[2,8,10, 11,12]

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